

Study on the Effects of Homepage VMD Cues on Online Consumer Decision-making

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Abstract

The current e-commerce market competition pattern is clear. Chances are very slim for those new entrants lacking capital advantage to obtain any competitive advantage. As the most active category on Internet market, apparel retailers are facing huge pressure in competition. Due to availability of information, rigid attributes like prices, fabrics and country of origin gradually lose competition values. Marketers began to take advantage of consumer participation in the age of Web2.0 and design marketing stimulus from the perceptual level. Based on the need of e-market practice, this paper tried to empirically test the relation between the aesthetic attribute, "likes" and consumer reactions on a mock social commerce website. Therefore, provide a theoretical reference and consumer analysis ideas for online apparel marketers.

Keywords: Clothing purchase; Online Consumer Behavior; Visual Merchandising; Visual stimuli

1. Introduction

The relationship between marketing stimulation and consumer behavior response has always been the focus of the market theory and marketing practice. With big data technology, a lot of quantifiable rational stimulation, such as commodity prices, country of origin, performance parameters and other marketing clues can be established through the causal links with consumer response using certain algorithm. However, it is difficult to establish the relationship between the aesthetic marketing stimuli with big data, which is closely related to the fashion products. But no matter from the common-sense level or from the marketing experience, there are always some basic relations, such as: clothing in line with people's aesthetic view are usually the bestsellers". In fact, even in Taobao stores, the competition among many small brands or even no-brands, not all products with similar price or similar class can get similar attention.

In the real business environment, the sales staff can determine the purchase intention of consumers to a certain extent depending on their experience. While in the Internet context, the behavior of consumers is actually more likely to be observed. And all consumer behavior can be stored in digital form. Marketers are expected to use these available resources effectively to better understand consumer behavior and then promote their commodities through proper marketing incentives. Under the S-O-R (stimulus-organism-response) paradigm, this paper focuses on the relationship between marketing stimuli and behavioral responses in the context of a mock social commerce website in order to provide some practical reference for marketers to improve VMD design based on online consumer behavior.

2. Visual merchandising stimulus and consumer behavior

2.1 current research status of visual marketing

Visual merchandising (VMD) is a strategic demonstration of an enterprise and its products to attract consumers and to maximize sales. VMD helps with marketing with store environment optimization, including merchandise display, store design, models, POS, lighting, graphics and logo system and so on^[1]. In fact, VMD strategy has always been the focus of fashion industry. A lot of research work has been done regarding the VMD in brick-and-mortar retail environment. While with the development of the fashion e-commerce, online visual marketing is getting more and more attention.

Szymanski and Hise found that consumer perceptions of site design might play major role in attracting consumers and was one of the dominant factors in consumer assessments of e-satisfaction^[2]. Usually, the more exciting the site is or the more mental pleasure it provides, the more likely purchase intention is to be triggered^[3]. Eroglu et al. grouped the environmental characteristics of the virtual "store" into two general categories as high-task cues and low-task cues. High-task relevant cues include verbal content related to the shopping goals (e.g., descriptions of the merchandise and price), pictures of the merchandise and navigation aids. Examples of low task-relevant cues are verbal content, which is unrelated to shopping goals, colors, borders and background patterns, typestyles and fonts, animation, music and sounds and so on^[4]. Various studies have been conducted regarding how VMD cues could affect consumer behavior, including the way of commodity display (2D or 3D, mannequin or real model) and richness of the displayed contents (diversity of pictures, picture zooming function, angle diversity, degree of match between clothing and environment). And these studies mainly center around stimulus of webmosphere and analyze how stimulus affects consumer response. That is, predict the purchase intention through the comparison of consumer psychological reaction.

Theoretical research regarding the relationship between aesthetic characteristics of the commodity and the response to consumer behavior is rare mainly because aesthetic characteristics is hard to be scaled. In addition, many previous studies have involved the relationship between word-of-mouth of online commodity and consumer purchase intention. But consumer online interaction is much richer in content in the era of the Web2.0. And even without user's experience, consumers can still interact and leave commodity related information, such as "likes". For this consumer interaction-generated marketing stimuli, relevant research is still seriously insufficient.

2.2 research hypothesis

Product appearance is a critical tool for enterprises to create differentiation and gain competitive advantage. Yamamotohe and Lambert testified that the aesthetic characteristics of industrial products affect the overall evaluation and the preference of the product^[5]. Product design determines the consumer's first impression of it and quickly conveys product advantages to consumers. In addition, the appearance of the product itself offers value. Many people prefer to purchase more beautiful products. And the aesthetic value of durable goods is usually more important to consumers. The main reason is that durable goods are often displayed to others in a long period of time, and some consumers are willing to give up part of functional attributes of products in the trade of aesthetics^[6]. Clothing is a necessity of human life. Its social attributes often convey information of aesthetic, literacy and identity of the wearer. Although in marketing experience, the relationship between product appearance and the purchase rate is common sense. In theory, little attention is paid to the effects of the aesthetic characteristics of commodity on consumer behavior. The reason is that the aesthetic features usually need to be specific. And personal aesthetic perception is difficult to be quantified. But in a certain period of time, views of aesthetics may reach in common (i.e. popularity or trend). Therefore, with the help of aesthetic evaluation index^[7], this paper uses 20 pre-assessed dresses of different aesthetic levels as stimuli to find out the relationship between aesthetics of clothing and consumer behavior. As for dresses, the higher of its aesthetic ratings the more attention it's going to get and more likely to be purchased. That is:

H1: commodity aesthetic rating is positively correlated with the number of clicks it gets

H2: commodity aesthetic rating is positively correlated with its purchase frequencies

The behavior of clicking "like" usually means one's support for the relevant content. The Facebook help center's description of "like" is: "it's a simple way to let people know what you like without commenting on the post". In academic research, "like" clicking is generally regarded as the interactive behavior based on online information or content. Only a few empirical studies related the "likes" with purchase frequencies. Brettel et al. proved the number of "likes" of a brand advertisements on its Facebook homepage had a strong influence on the sales in the long term (due to the lag effect)^[8]. In the social commerce context, the "like" icon is generally located below the picture or hidden in the picture above (it shows only when the mouse slide over the picture). Regarding the type of VMD cues, it belongs to low stimulus category. However, due to the essence of "like" clicking is an expression of support for a message, the number of "likes" therefore indicates the degree of support by consumers. It is believed that the higher the number of initial "likes" the easier the commodity is purchased or paid attention to. And the higher the increased number of "likes" the easier the commodity is purchased or paid attention to. That is:

H3: the initial number of "likes" of a commodity is positively correlated with the number of clicks it gets

H4: the initial number of "likes" of a commodity is positively correlated with its purchase frequencies

H5: the increased number of "likes" of a commodity is positively correlated with the number of clicks it gets

H6: the increased number of "likes" of a commodity is positively correlated with its purchase frequencies

3. Research method and data collecting

This study made a mock social commerce website in order to collect data of consumer behavior and compare the influence of

visual stimuli factors. It mixed different features of commodities (aesthetic rating, number of likes, and position of display) to avoid synergistic effect. For example, commodities of high aesthetic ratings won't all end in best display locations. This study involved a total of 20 dresses with 10 spring/summer and 10 autumn/winter styles to avoid the impact of seasonal factors. Commodity aesthetics are rated by 20 female college students respectively on the three dimensions of attraction, fashionable and fondness and then weighted mean. Display position on homepage is vertically divided into upper, middle and lower, and horizontally divided into left, middle and right. The location of dresses not on the homepage is labelled as "0". Dress classification page includes a total of two pages with ten items on each page. And the number of "likes" on each dress value is also set initially. The homepage of the mock website is shown in Figure1. The characteristics of the related stimuli are shown in table 1.

Figure 1 Homepage of the mock website

Table1 VMD stimulus of dresses on the mock website

Style No. of dress	Aesth-etic rating	Location on homepage	Locati-on in categor-y	Initial likes	Style No. of dress	Aesth-etic rating	Location on homepage	Locati-on in category	Initial likes
0001	4.38	none/0	2	2	0011	3.81	center/5	1	25
0002	5.32	lower left/7	2	2	0012	4.37	none/0	1	2
0003	3.8	none/0	2	1	0013	4.48	none/0	1	1
0004	3.7	upper left/1	1	12	0014	4.76	lower right/9	1	21
0005	3.79	upper left/1	1	8	0015	4.06	center right/6	1	15
0006	4.39	center left/4	2	6	0016	4.36	none/0	1	0
0007	4.41	center left/4	2	4	0017	4.58	upper right/3	1	11
0008	4.43	none/0	2	1	0018	5.04	upper center/2	1	6
0009	4.66	lower left/7	2	4	0019	5.06	none/0	1	0
0010	3.79	none/0	2	1	0020	4.67	lower center /8	1	12

Based on the design of stimulus factors, female college students between 18 and 25 years old were invited by e-mail to

register and buy a dress (without paying) on the mock social commerce website. And they were told to have a chance to receive the purchased dress for free. The backstage of the mock website records behavioral data of each registered object. It finally sorted out 291 registered names. After the elimination of repeated registration, leaving after registration and failure to complete the required task, a total of 205 valid samples with behavioral data were recovered with the effective rate of 70%.

4. correlation analysis between behavioral data and stimulus variables

There is no doubt that the display location has an important impact on the consumer's attention and purchase decisions. However, the merits of commodity display location cannot be directly converted into precise data form. Therefore, in the analysis of the relationships between purchase and commodity aesthetic evaluation as well as number of “likes”, other factors need to be controlled.

1) When the relationship between aesthetic rating and behavior is analyzed, factors of display locations and initial likes are both dealt as control variables. Partial correlation analysis showed that significant positive linear correlations exist between the aesthetic rating of a commodity and its purchase frequency, number of clicks, number of clicking objects, purchase conversion rate (purchase frequency / click frequency) of it, non-purchase clicks on it and consumer purchase ratio (purchase frequency / total number of objects clicked it) as shown in table 2.

2) Similarly, when the relationship between initial likes and behavior is analyzed, factors of display locations and aesthetic rating are both dealt as control variables. Partial correlation analysis showed that significant positive linear correlations don't exist between the initial likes of a commodity and its purchase frequency, number of clicks, number of clicking objects, purchase conversion rate (purchase frequency / click frequency) of it, non-purchase clicks on it and consumer purchase ratio (purchase frequency / total number of objects clicked it) as shown in table 2.

Table2 Partial correlation coefficient between consumer behavior and stimulus variables

Dependent variables	Control variables	Aesthetic rating	Control variables	Initial likes	increased likes
purchase frequency	location on homepage & location in category & initial likes	0.65**	location on homepage & location in category & aesthetic rating	0.33	0.34
number of clicks		0.65**		0.36	0.39
number of clicking objects		0.53*		0.32	0.32
purchase conversion rate		0.55*		0.34	0.39
non-purchase clicks		0.64**		0.36	0.39
consumer purchase ratio		0.68**		0.40	0.35

(* significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.01 level)

To sum up, hypotheses H1, H2 are supported, while H3-H6 are not supported. According to this conclusion, set display locations aside, aesthetic rating of a dress not only has a significant impact on consumers' clicks (number of clicks, number of clicking objects, non-purchase clicks) but also on purchase (purchase frequency, purchase conversion rate, consumer purchase ratio). That is, the good appearance of a dress may attract more attention and purchase. This also shows that, even in the social commerce context with heuristic traits, purchase decision tend to be rational overall.

Regarding the interactive behavior of like clicking, the total increased number of likes clicked by objects is 29 from the 20 different samples (less than 10% of the sample size). The main reason for this phenomenon is that the scenario set in this study is for objects to fulfill a purchase task. And compared to interaction, purchase belongs to high task category. That is, even in the context with interactive function, if the decision is clearly high task oriented, information interaction is easily to be ignored as a low task by consumers. In addition, there is no significant linear correlation between initial likes of a commodity and its purchase frequency. The result is essentially consistent with previous research. First, the icon of like on the social commerce website is very weak in visual impact. And the essence of like is a kind of pre-purchase preference for the commodity which does not necessarily convey any user's experience and thus can barely influence purchase in a high-task scenario. This phenomenon at least indicates “like” on social commerce website belong to low-task cue class. Secondly, according to the previous research finding that “likes” of advertising has significant positive effect on sales in the long run, the relationship between the number of likes and sales volume is in fact the relationship between the rate of market acceptance and the sales volume. In the context design of this paper,

the number of initial likes of dress is not an objective reflection from the market. And the empirical results show that in high task oriented scenario, the number of initial likes can neither influence consumer's attention, nor trigger purchase.

5. Main findings and conclusion

This study analyzed the relationship between online VMD cues and consumer decision-making. Regarding commodity type like dress, in the high-task oriented scenario (with purchase intention), key attributes (aesthetics for dress) of products play a major role in consumer decision-making. While interactive cues (number of initial "likes") with no user experience involved does not have significant influence on consumer behavior. With the principal found by this paper, marketers may get a clear idea of how to use click-stream data to determine the most important VMD factors in online consumer decision-making and make their everyday work more efficient.

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